

uppermost leaf sheath enclosing the infected internode remained healthy. Sections of tissues of the uppermost internode rotted and were covered with sooty spore masses. In late infection, grains developed poorly. The disease was more severe in dry fields than in wet

fields.

When microscopically examined, diseased samples collected from different rice-growing valley areas in the State consistently showed *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. The pathogen was isolated on rice straw extract agar medium and its

pathogenicity proved.

The sudden spread of the disease seems to have been influenced by cultivation of high-yielding, susceptible rice varieties and by a long dry spell during late growth stage. □

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Predators of rice insect pests in Chhattishgarh region, Madhya Pradesh, India

D. Bhardwaj and A. D. Pawar, Central Biological Control Station, Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, India

Madhya Pradesh is situated between latitude 17° and 26°N and longitude 74° and 84°E. Rice is the predominant crop in Chhattishgarh, which has mixed red and yellow soil, 1,400-1,600 mm average rainfall, 85-95% average humidity, and

Predators of rice insect pests in Chhattishgarh region, Madhya Pradesh, India, 1984-86.

Predators	Prevalence
I Araneida	
Tetragnathidae	High
<i>Tetragnatha mandibulata</i>	
Lycosidae	
<i>Lycosa pseudoannulata</i>	Moderate
II Orthoptera	
Tettigoniidae	
<i>Conocephalus longipennis</i>	Moderate
III Odonota	
Coenagrionidae	
<i>Ischnura</i> sp.	Low
<i>Agriocnemis pygmaea</i>	High
IV Coleoptera	
Carabidae	Moderate
<i>Ophionea nigrofasciata</i>	
<i>Casnoidea indica</i>	Low
Coccinellidae	
<i>Coccinella arcuata</i>	Moderate
<i>Menochilus sexmaculata</i>	Low
<i>Scymnus postpinctus</i>	Low
Staphylinidae	
<i>Paederus fuscipes</i>	High
V Hemiptera	
Miridae	High
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	
Gerridae	Moderate
<i>Limnogonus</i> sp.	
<i>Microvelia</i> sp.	Moderate
Nabidae	
<i>Tropiconabis capsiformis</i>	Moderate

20-30 °C temperature during the Jun-Sep monsoon. Monsoon rice cultivation favors insect multiplication.

We counted natural enemies of monsoon rice pests in 1984-86 (see table). □

Effect of insecticides on eggs of *Brevennia rehi* (Lindinger)

M. Gopalan, N. C. Radja, and G. Balasubramanian, Centre for Plant Protection Studies, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We tested the ovicidal action of 11 insecticides in the laboratory (see table).

For each treatment, 50 eggs were

placed in a petri dish lined with moist filter paper and sprayed with 1 ml spray solution, using an atomizer.

Eggs that hatched were counted every 15 min for 3 d. Data were converted into arc sin values and corrected for natural mortality using Abbott's formula.

BPMC 0.25 kg ai/ha delayed hatching most, and crawlers that hatched, died. □

Effect of insecticides on hatchability of *B. rehi* eggs.^a Coimbatore, India.

Insecticide	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Hatchability (%)	Mortality (%)
Endosulfan	0.33	11 def	31 de
Phosphamidon	0.25	13 efg	22 f
Monocrotophos	0.20	10 def	36 de
Fenthion	0.50	11 cde	34 de
Chlorpyrifos	0.35	12 efg	22 f
Methyl demeton	0.125	10 c	39 d
Dimethoate	0.15	8 cd	51 c
Phosalone	0.35	12 efg	23 f
Biphenyl methyl carbamate	0.25	2 a	88 a
Deltamethrin	0.01	14 fg	14 g
Carbaryl	0.5	7 b	58 b
Control	-	14 g	-

^a Mean of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are arc sin transformed values. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

Insect pests on main and ratoon rice

A.K. Chakravarthy, Regional Research Station, Mudigere 577132, India

Intan, a popular irrigated rice variety in the hilly region of Karnataka, was sown 5 Jul 1984 and 7 Jun 1985 in 8- × 1- ×

0.1-m nursery beds. Seedlings were transplanted 2 Aug 1984 in 64-m² plots and 13 Jul 1985 in 66-m² plots with 4 replications.

To supplement natural buildup of insect population, 15-20 20-m-long rows were maintained on each side of the experimental field. No insecticides were